

GRADIENT MATERIALS INTERFACE FOR HIGH-TEMP SENSOR MODULES

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ABSTRACT

Placing electronics sensor modules at high temperature regime is getting increasingly important for accurately monitoring performance life of aircraft engines or other sensitive thermal components. Electronics sensor modules capable of operating at high temperature also eliminates parasitic electronics cooling accessories and thus enables both weight and cost savings [1]. Usually in high temperature electronics modules, the electronics chips (dies) are bonded to the packaging board (heat sink) via a metalized dielectric substrate (heat spreader) in between, known to be are the directly bonded copper (DBC) or directly bonded alumina (DBA). In this work, a materials solution for the CTE mismatch issues in DBC is presented with two-phase amorphous alloy composition via Molecular Dynamics (MD) simulation. A two-phase Cu/Zr amorphous alloy composition of 0-45% Cu composition appears to show promise to match with the CTEs of ceramic substrates (such as AlN). This type of hybrid material composition is thus expected to provide a possible desirable material solution towards enhancing the fatigue life in high temperature electronics modules.

1 INTRODUCTION

Placing electronics sensor modules at high temperature regime is getting increasingly important for accurately monitoring performance life of aircraft engines or other sensitive thermal components. Electronics sensor modules capable of operating at high temperature also eliminates parasitic electronics cooling accessories and thus enables both weight and cost savings [1]. Usually in electronics modules, the electronics chips (dies) are bonded to the packaging board (heat sink) via a metalized dielectric substrate (heat spreader) in between. There is a significant mismatch of coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) in these materials used in bonding the modules. In the case of high temperature electronics modules (or power electronics) thermal stress build-up during thermal cycling is the biggest driver of mechanical failure due to CTE mismatch. The thermal cycles can be driven by both the environment (heated compartments such as engine bays) as well as the electronics generating high temperatures as well (junction temperature). In addition turning the electronics between on/off periods will also generate many thermal cycles. Moreover, these devices generate heat during its operation, thus hot environment operation of these devices makes the situation worse. Typical failure modes are fracturing within the ceramic substrate or separation at the interface due to loss of interface adhesion.

Figure 1. Delaminated interfaces (circled in red) in die/substrate assembly after 100 cycles from -55°C to 200°C dual chamber air-air temperature shock [3]

In current practice, the devices and dies have metallic contacts deposited on the semiconductor with significant mismatch in CTE between the metal and semiconductor, as stated above. Even more challenging is the circuit board material employed for power electronics. Often a high thermal conductive ceramic such as aluminum nitride ($k \sim 170 \text{ W/m-K}$) or silicon nitride ($k \sim 90 \text{ W/m-K}$) is utilized instead of the typical fiberglass substrate ($k \sim 0.3 \text{ W/m-K}$). The copper cladding on ceramics or SiC, often 100's of microns thick, is to provide high current traces with low resistance, which Exacerbating the CTE situation. The shear forces generated by the mismatch in CTE increase with the thickness of the bulk materials (ceramic and copper). These metalized (copper cladded) dielectric substrates, prevalent in high temperature electronics, are typically the directly bonded copper (DBC) or

directly bonded alumina (DBA) on ceramic materials with SiC or GaN devices soldered to the DBC/DBA. Primary failure modes in electronics modules, as stated earlier and also observed upon thermal cycling, are either in the form of delamination of the surfaces of the two surfaces that DBC/DBA interfaces with chips (dies) or the packaging board (heat sink) or the DBC/DBA materials failure (Fig. 1) [2]. The cause of these failure modes is attributed to the thermal stress induced by the thermal expansion coefficient mismatch between the dissimilar materials. Materials thermal conductivity also has a role in this materials failure process. Further, a comparatively low thermal conductivity in this materials composition (e.g., AlN as compared to Cu in DBC) induces temperature build-up, which in turn induces a ran-away material degradation phenomena adversely affecting to these interface failure processes.

A way of addressing this interface failure issue is to introduce a gradient materials composition to minimize the CTE mismatch issue, particularly in DBCs. The objective of this work is to pursue materials design, combined with materials processing to design DBC and packaging board (metal-ceramic) interface to enhance thermal cycle fatigue life.

2 THERMAL CYCLING OF DBC SAMPLES

In order to determine the extent and severity of the thermal stress build-up affecting the materials failure in DBCs (ceramic (AlN) with Cu cladding on both surfaces), thermal cycling of standalone DBC specimens was performed three different temperature ranges till specimen materials failure, utilizing a thermomechanical analyzer (TMA) and one centimeter square test sample. A TA Instruments Q400 TMA with expansion probe was utilized for this purpose. In addition to providing the thermal cycle environment, the TMA also precisely measures changes in sample thickness with accuracy less than a micrometer. The onset of fracturing due to thermal cycling can be monitored high precision. Ceramic (AlN) thickness is 0.63 mm with 0.3mm Cu each side (Remtec, Inc). Three temperature range of the thermal cycling is pursues: from -55 C to either 100 °C, 150 °C, or 300 °C. Table 1 indicates the number of cycles till the onset of fracturing, determined by the onset of sharp displacement change in TMA test, as shown in Figure 2. In all cases the fracture failure is within the Ceramic layer. From the location of the failure it can be inferred that the stress is being transferred away from the interface to the interior of the bulk layer. A figure of merit can be utilized to estimate the residual stress based on the difference in coefficient of thermal expansion of the ceramic and metal, the temperature difference and a geometric average of the elastic modulus, $\sigma = (\Delta\alpha \Delta T E_m E_c) / (E_m + E_c)$. Here, both ceramic (AlN) and Cu are considered of equal thickness, E_m and E_c are

the elastic moduli of metal (Cu) and ceramic (AlN) respectively, $\Delta\alpha$ and ΔT are CTE and temperature difference, respectively.

TABLE 1 Number of Cycles till Failure

Temperature range	Failure cycle	$\Delta\sigma$, GPa
-55 C to 100 °C	> 200	0.163
-55 C to 150 °C	34	0.216
-55 C to 300 °C	5	0.374

The change in residual stress ($\Delta\sigma$) for the temperature difference of cycling is also given in Table 1 for each of the cases. The compressive strength of aluminum nitride (AlN) is typically 2.3 GPa whereas the tensile strength is 0.23 GPa. As shown in Table 1, the residual stress at 150 and 300°C cycling cases are close to and exceeding the tensile strength of AlN. From this one can hypothesize there is a role for multifunctional interfaces to reduce the stress distributed to the bulk of the ceramic in order to allow temperature cycles over a wider temperature range while maintaining good thermal transport across the interface, which is the objective of this study.

Figure 3. Representative DBC interface materials configuration

In the following section we present a computational approach of designing a hybrid materials configuration, an amorphous metal alloy, as a replacement of the Cu cladding on ceramic. The goal of this design is to define an alloy composition of CTE close to that of the ceramic materials possessing desirable thermal

conductivity, as depicted in Figure 3.

3 HYBRID AMORPHOUS Cu/Zr ALLOY DESIGN

In this study we pursued a molecular dynamics (MD) computational approach to define a hybrid Cu/Zr alloy composition to replace Cu cladding on ceramics for DBCs for possible application as

conductive lead materials for power electronics. The CTE of Cu and Zr are 16.4 and $5.7 \times 10^{-6}/\text{K}$, respectively, and the respective thermal conductivity values are 401 and 16.7 W/m-K. We postulated that alloying of these two materials would significantly lower CTE of that of Cu and the alloy would have desirable thermal conductivity.

The goal of this modeling research is predicting the coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) of Cu/Zr bulk amorphous alloys in broad composition range. The CTE prediction is based on material characterization on a molecular level, and may be applicable to other multicomponent systems such as other bulk metallic glasses or miscible polymeric blends. The Zr/Cu alloy seems like a natural choice for creating an interface between semiconductor chip material and Cu leads. Pure Zr metal ensures very low CTE $5.7 \times 10^{-6}/\text{K}$, approaching those of the ceramics (e.g., AlN – $4.8 \times 10^{-6}/\text{K}$), and is capable of creating good chemical bonding with the ceramic substrate. It is expected therefore that Zr lead could withstand multiple temperature cycles without breaking at the interface. Furthermore, the sharp interface between the lead and the chip (like it is implemented in the common directly bonded copper setup) would be replaced with a relatively thick layer of Zr/Cu alloy with molar composition gradually changing from pure Zr to the increased Cu content far away from the ceramics. This would allow the distribution of thermal stresses throughout the volume of the lead and avoid material crackling upon thermal cycling. The opposite side of the lead would be composed of pure Cu to allow stress-free connection to copper wiring. The modeling would allow choosing the required lead layer thickness and selecting the appropriate composition gradient profile for deposition to minimize mechanical stresses due to CTE mismatch.

The Cu/Zr alloys with molar composition between 35 and 65% Cu form well-known binary bulk metallic glasses (BMG) that has been studied for approximately two decades [3]. Binary metallic glasses generally demonstrate poor glass forming ability, with only four known exceptions Cu/Zr, Cu/Hf, Ni/Nb and Ca/Al compositions [4]. Using binary systems instead of more stable tertiary systems would make the deposition process easier, while the thermodynamic stability of binary glassy system suggests that it will not crystallize with degradation of properties and will stay amorphous after the deposition. The CTE prediction through quantitative material characterization involves the selection of appropriate structural parameters, which in case our system will be obtained from a molecular level, MD, modeling. Unlike crystals, the molecular structure of glassy materials could not be easily characterized and each atom has the unique environment formed by its neighbors, which is taken into consideration for the MD simulation.

3(a) SIMULATION SET UP

A series of MD runs was conducted in the temperature range 250-1000 K using Nose-Hoover thermostat, Parrinello-Rahman barostat and periodic boundary conditions (PBC) as implemented in LAMMPS [5] program. Random amorphous structures containing 1440 atoms each were generated using in-house Monte Carlo packing technique with geometrical constraints. An independent replica of random amorphous structure was generated for each MD run. Structure was further optimized by LAMMPS energy minimization followed by NPT MD run for 5 ns. The recorded atom trajectories for each run were used to analyze molecular structure and dynamics using Voronoi polyhedra analysis using XenoView [6] program.

The effective atom media EAM potential [7] was used to model interatomic interactions in Cu/Zr amorphous alloys. The effective atom media (EAM) potential is probably the most suitable classical force field suggested for metals. This is a many-body potential in tabulated form that uses second order approximation to tight binding theory, and combines high computational efficiency with high accuracy. Relatively fast simulation setup (compared with,

for instance, DFT) allows us to perform a big number of molecular dynamics simulations of statistically independent structures, achieving proper averaging of structural parameters.

3(b) SIMULATION RESULTS

The sample snapshots of MD simulation structures for three different compositions are shown in Fig.4. Each structure contains uniformly mixed Cu and Zr atoms packed in approximately cubic box with periodic boundaries. The total number of atoms is 1440 for all studied structures, and the number

of Cu and Zr atoms changes according to molar composition. All alloyed structures in the composition range 5-95 % Cu content remain amorphous for all simulation conditions (250-1000 K temperature

range, atmospheric pressure, and up to 10 ns of the simulation time). Both pure Cu and pure Zr structures may quickly and spontaneously crystallize at any time during MD run, creating a polycrystalline-type structure as shown in Fig.5. These results are in agreement with thermodynamically calculated amorphization composition range of for rapidly quenched Cu/Zr alloys [8].

The CTE of Zr, as shown in Fig. 6, is close to that of AlN. Thus, hybrid layer of Zr/Cu, where Zr is interfacing with AlN surface is envisioned. Turchanin, et al [9] has recently shown in their theoretical study that a certain combination of Zr/Cu amorphous mixture is thermodynamically stable. Since the thickness this hybrid layer is limited to a few nanometers (near the atomic scale), simple rule of mixture of the bulk CTEs of these two materials is not expected to provide accurate estimate of the resultant CTE. Thus, a molecular dynamics (MD) simulation was performed to predict and analyze the density, thermal conductivity and CTE of the Zr/Cu mixture. The CTE variation of the fractional Zr/Cu composition is shown in Fig. 6. It is worth to note that the CTE of Zr/Cu hybrid monotonically increases with increasing Cu content up to 25 percent, after which the value of its CTE oscillates. The cause of this oscillation needs to be studied further, perhaps this could be due to some phase agglomeration [10], an indication of which is inferred from the density derivative (Fig. 6, green curve of its values on the right axis) that follows qualitatively similarly to CTE variation with changing Cu/Zr composition. The two-phase agglomeration related density fluctuation and its correlation with CTE can possibly be studied as suggested by Turner [11]. Along with materials modeling, thin film processing via a dual source

PLD (plasma laser deposition) of this hybrid mixture and its materials morphology characterization (SEM, TEM) is being pursued and will be presented in a later publication.

4 SUMMARY

A hybrid Cu/Zr interface layer is proposed to mitigate the thermal stress induced interface delamination in high temperature electronics sensor modules. The current simulation indicates that the Cu/Zr amorphous alloy appears to be a good material composition to mitigate the interface CTE mismatch problem encountered in high temperature electronics. It is worth to mention that the composition range of 0-45 % mol. of Cu with Zr covers the whole range of CTE from ceramics (such as AlN), thus, such two-phase alloy composition could be a material solution for this purpose. In addition

to this, the stable amorphous compositions (40-70% Cu mol.) show small variation of CTE with Cu content along with a distinct dip in CTE for Cu-rich (of Cu content ~ 80%) alloys. This possibly be explained by change in the bulk modulus for these compositions, which will be analyzed in a subsequent work.

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